

Human Symptom Analysis for Multi-Disease and Prediction using PyCharm and Machine Learning

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Abstract— In recent years, machine learning frameworks for medical analysis have predominantly focused on individual diseases, with separate models developed for conditions like skin diseases, cancer, and diabetes. However, these systems are often limited in their ability to predict multiple diseases simultaneously using a single approach. This research proposes a machine learning-based method for predicting the prognosis of various diseases through a unified system. The study analyzes a range of diseases, including diabetes, heart disease, retinopathy, breast cancer, and lung diseases, using a variety of patient symptoms. The system is designed to incorporate additional conditions, such as skin disorders and fever, in future iterations. Several machine learning algorithms, including Linear Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, and Logistic Regression, are applied to the datasets for comprehensive multi-disease analysis. The novelty of this approach lies in its ability to account for a wide array of factors that contribute to disease prediction, allowing for a more complete understanding of potential health risks. For example, while existing systems for diabetes diagnosis typically consider a limited set of factors like cholesterol, blood pressure, and skin thickness, this method aims to incorporate a broader spectrum of variables. The goal of this research is to enhance disease monitoring, track patient progress more effectively, and provide early warnings to reduce mortality rates. The analysis is conducted using PyCharm IDE, Jupyter, and Python, with the Naive Bayes algorithm used to calculate disease probability, ensuring higher accuracy in predictions. **Keywords—** Machine Learning, Linear Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Logistic Regression and Naive Bayes algorithm.

1. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

The machine learning algorithm comprises of two phases with the first being the Training Phase and the second being the Testing Phase. Machine learning technology has been struggling from past decades involving the anticipation of the type of disease found on the base of patient's symptoms and past reports of said patient. Healthcare problems can be resolved expeditiously with the help of ML Technology.

Hence we are implementing complete ML concepts for maintaining the informaton of the patient's health.

Machine Learning model aids in building models to get quickly cleaned and processed to allow faster delivery of results. With this system, doctors are further capable of making good decisions related to the patient diagnoses resulting in good treatment with simultaneous provision in improvement of the patient's healthcare services. The prime example is to pioneer machine learning in the medical field, healthcare.

Existing work is done on unstructured textual data to provide better efficiency over the large data. To forecast diseases, the current approach involves utilizing linear regression, KNN, and decision tree algorithms.

The existing systems in Healthcare, analysis is on performed only on a single disease that is considered or made at any given time.

Consider an example to analyze diabetes or diabetes retinopathy or used to predict heart disease shown in the article, similarly another articles on lung disease for each use case focus on a particle disease. The patient's health reports, help in to analyze in an organization, It may use many models to deploy. However, the approach taken is suitable to analyze only one disease. Mortality rates have increasingly become common due to not able to find the problem the patient is infected within the time.

The patient may be recovered from one disease but, they may be troubled with some other diseases later..

For example, in this context, diabetes presents a heightened risk of various health complications, such as heart disease, neuropathy, retinopathy, deafness, and dementedness. This article focuses on the analysis of datasets related to diabetes, retinopathy, lung disease, heart disease, and cancer detection. However, further iterations of this

analysis may incorporate additional diseases, such as skin conditions, fever-related ailments, and more. The flexibility of this analysis framework allows for the seamless inclusion of new diseases. To integrate a new disease into the existing API, developers need to add the relevant model file. When creating a model for a new disease, developers are required to prepare a Python relish record to save the model's behavior. Subsequently, developers will send the stored records to recover the behavior of the model.

Users can employ this system to analyze a patient's health condition, predicting a specific disease. Since the medical report include factors relevant to the prediction of another diseases, provides the yielding of specifying most related diseases. The dominate goal of this project is to reduce the death rate by providing early warnings to patients based on their health conditions. Consolidating models and predictions for multiple diseases in a single platform offers the potential to reduce the cost of patient analysis.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

As per records of American Diabetes Association (ADA) "Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes" includes ADA's have been recommending and also providing various components for diabetes patient and helps in evaluate the quality of care for them. A multidisciplinary expert committee Associates of the ADA Professional Practice, are responsible for updating the Standards of Care yearly base at professional.diabetes.org/SOC [1].

The dependence on sensor device technology has effected in saving a lot of electronic data specially in the health care area. That lead for the heavy demand or the health care professionals and the Doctors. Further it lead for the research on the prediction of the symptoms of the diseases and the illness. It helps in prediction it in early stage of the disease. However, Machine Learning technology had been more beneficial in the solving the issues in the medical area. Disease Prediction is a Machine Learning based system which primarily works to the symptoms given by a user given by Nidhi Kosarkar et.al [2].

The nervous system in humans mainly links with the spinal cord, nerves and brain. It controls all the functionality of the body. All the body parts are working with the support of the nervous system. This paper discusses on unconfined care state structure excavation and study the practicability of detection neurological diseases. human body devices use IoT networks utilizes certain levels of range to seizure data for the occurrence. The test reports show whether the test taken is positive or negative with the support of extracted amplitude shown in the article. They applied various algorithms to show the different categorizes. The decision tree algorithm shows improved reports among the applied machine learning algorithms by Shanmuga Sundari et.al [3].

Mahmood Hussain Kadhem et.al [4] Data mining (DM) helps in various applications in the health care area. DM helps in finding various practices used for analyze or to predict the diseases supported on the factors of the diseases. Its also used to examine the occurrence of it and taken care for a group of patients on the various characteristics and parameters provided. It presents the quality of DM to evolve a anticipation framework for a presumptive diagnosis of two familiar with urinary diseases: the acute inflammation of the urinary bladder and nephritis of renal pelvis. The information used in this casestudy includes varity of features which are

important in diagnosing any patient with an acute inflammation of urinary bladder or nephritis. The decision tree (J48) provides a better efficiency and ability in anticipation, and it also helps in categorize the patients' data with the diseases symptoms. The analyzed information helps in training of the 10-fold cross validation. By the DT an acute urinary bladder and nephritis has been rendered .

Similarly the Skin cancer cases around the universe has increased in past decade. As per the World Health organization (WHO), more than 3 million cases of skin cancer diseases are noticed every year around the world soon the finding the diseases early helps in discovery of the diagnoses of the disease and it is very important to increase patient predictive. By using of Deep learning model, it has shown in a variety of medical image processing tasks recently. To build a deep learning model using Convolution Neural Network (CNN) for early detection of the skin cancer diseases has been done with the support of few skin images. This framework is designed by using various predominant characteristic of skin cancer images for anticipation. To achieve a 95% accuracy rate, the model uses a hybrid combination of activation functions across three distinct hidden layers. The model can predict values of unseen data with high accuracy. In the sphere of medicine and healthcare, the work that has been done is anticipated to be a useful model for the early diagnosis of skin cancer.

3. ANALYSI OF THE DISEASES

3.1. Acute Disease. As per to United State National Center for Health Statistics, acute diseases are those that are there for a long time. These diseases are can not be diagnosed by medication nor ventilated by medication. the most common factor of acute diseases is the use of tobacco, rheumatic diet habits, and lack of physical exercise programs. This disease can normally be caused in elderring people. acute diseases consider cardiovascular disease, cancer, diabetes, arthritis, obesity, seizures, with difficulty in oral health and epilepsy [5].

Lack of nutrition food and physical exercises lead to many diseases few are Cardiovascular disease which adds heart disease and stroke, which may lead to death. The intake of tobacco and other harmful food items. once the activities are changed the patient will be better and in good healthy condition [6].

The list goes many that is cardiovascular disease, cancer like breast cancer, colon cancer and lung cancer are the dangerous problems. These disease are prevented by early detection with proper dataset generated by the IoT sensors time which needed to note the values.

The acute disease like arthritis damages the inflammation in the body joints, reasons for body pain, and clumsiness which grows as age increases. New methods are present which can reduce the cost-effective methods that reduces the causes by performing few simple exercises on park regularly [7].

One of the most common and highly expensive disease is Diabetes. Its effectiveness of diabetes is controlled by self controlling and detection of the disease early [17]. One of the most common in from the years 1980, obesity is popular in adults for all age peoples. The risk of getting high blood pressure (BP), heart diseases, diabetes, and arthritis are caused by the overweight of the Person.

The disease is same among all age people, especially in elders and youngsters. The health issues are very important problem which need to be addressed with quick attention of older people health condition. It is very crucial issue, The affects a the normal daily actions of a person such as speaking, chewing, and maintain a nutritional diet plan given by Epilepsy and seizures are expensive treatment [18].

The Majority of acute diseases are predicted by proposed system. It takes the data as input to the machine learning model of structured type. In proposed system, the users will provide all the health problems from which he or she is suffering. The health problem symptoms are sent to the ML model to guess the diseases. Intelligent Algorithms are applied to give better results. Since the proposed system predicts disease based on the patients inputs. The proposed system utilize Machine Learning Technology. Using the symptoms prediction is done with the use of Naïve Bayes algorithm. For the categorization KNN algorithm is used, Logistic regression is helps in infusion characteristic which are having best impact value, the Decision tree is helps to make in small dataset which is of big dataset. The disease predicted by the model is the final output.

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed architecture of the disease prediction is based on the data gathered from the patients for diagnosing, here a complete information of the diseases is considered as the dataset, where we gather different symptoms of diseases like heart disease data set, lung disease datasets, brain disease dataset etc., for preparation of the model, and disease prediction need to be done. Initially collection of data is done from the body sensors devices. The proposed system gathers the unstructured and structured information gathered from them. Next they are preprocessed and divided in two sets that is cleansed and test data sets. Later training data set is trained with the ML algorithms such as Navies, KNN and CNN for certain times to have better accuracy in prediction of the output. After number of time periods, It reaches the expected target, hence the testing of the model is ready.

Once the dataset is tested with the model there is need to verify the execution of the model with another new collection of data which has not undergone training is considered. The proposed system achieves the desirable results in test data with better accuracy and deployed as shown in Figure 1.

4.1. Data Accumulation: Body sensor devices provides original data that includes organized information of the patient's primary data considering statistics, living environment, and lab test consequence. The unorganized data of the disease symptoms that undergoing by the patient and the discussions with the doctor. Similarly the patient's personal details like name, ID, sex and address are preserved their privacy are excluded.

Figure 1. Architecture of the disease prediction

4.2. Preprocessing: The structured data are preprocessed for missing information in the datasets. Therefore, its necessary to updated data that is missed or withdraw or change them to improve the standard of the data set. It also terminates the commas, punctuation, and white space while performing the preprocessing. After successful completion of the preprocessing of data, it is then subjected to characteristic activity preceded with several predictions.

4.3. Description of Model: The data set includes both unstructured and structured collection as per above gathered information. The structured information consists patient statistics and the information relevant that caused the disease. patient's living surroundings, testing ground test consequence, and shown in the tabular format which shows the effect of the diseases. The data which is unstructured consists patient's diseases grounds and information regarding the interrogatory from the doctors that is in the format of texture. To get a more precise outcome based unstructured data is the advantage of the prediction. The information is generally is divide into 80% for training and 20% for testing.

Algorithm 1: Navie’s Bayees Algorithms on Data set

Implementing activation function as
 D Dataset as lambda y: (1)/(1+ mx.exp1(-a)
 # Sigmoid func.

Begin

Input:mx.random.randb[6 2]
HLayer-1= stimulation (mx.dot(A1,input)+c1)
Hlayer-2= Stimulation (mx.dot(A2,Hlayer-1)+c2)
Output: mx.dot(A3,Hlayer-2)+c3
Where A1,A2,A3,c1,c2,c3 are learnable parameters

End

Fig.2. Prediction bar for learnable parameters

Fig.3. Comparison of Algorithms

5. RESULTS

Here we Consider three diseases dataset which are diabetes, Heart Cancer, Liver failure then we integrated those dataset as one dataset then we pre processed the data and we removed null values and made it clean data and split dataset into two datasets which are Testing and Training Dataset and finally Predicted Disease based on symptoms of the person by using , Random Forest, Decision Tree,Linear Regression, Logistic Regression. Then we finally conclude which algorithm is better based on its Accuracy.

Algorithm	Packages	Functions	Parameters	Remarks
Decision Tree	Sklearn	tree.decisiontreeclassifier()	Symptoms(vomiting,constipation,cough,headache,general arches,pain)	Classification of Symptoms
	sklearn.metrics	accuracy_score Confusion_matrix		Accuracy is 0.9512
	sqlite3	Connect() Execute() Commit()		Storing the symptoms in the database
Random Forest	Sklearn.ensemble	RandomForestClassifier()	Symptoms(Vomiting, breathlessness, sweating, chestpain)	Classification of Symptoms
		accuracy_score Confusion_matrix		Accuracy is 0.9512
		Connect() Execute() Commit()		Storing the symptoms in the database
Logistic Regression	Sklearn.linear_model	LogisticRegression()	Symptoms	Classification of symptoms
		accuracy_score Confusion_matrix		Accuracy is 0.8415
		Connect() Execute() Commit()		Storing the symptoms in the database
Linear Regression	glm() - Fitting Generalized Linear Models	glm()	Symptoms(cpi-Consumer Price Index), Age	Accuracy is 0.7653

Comparison :

Algorithm	Accuracy(%)
Decision Tree	0.9512
Random Forest(13)	0.9512
Linear Regression(14)	0.7653
Logistic Regression(15)	0.8415

6. CONCLUSION

The disease prediction system uses user symptoms to predict diseases, with an average prediction accuracy of

100%. Implemented using the Grails framework, it offers a easy environment accessible from anywhere. The system uses Decision Tree, Unplanned Forest, and Naïve Bayes algorithms for disease prediction, with accuracy is good. The system's performance and limitations may inform future developers and promote personalized patient care. The Prediction of Disease done with this framework was more success. The whole environment is very easy to use and simple to get the results for prediction. It provides the better accuracy based on the patients data. The entire system works on the prediction of the diseases with help of Machine learning algorithms and get the best results in diagnosing the patients. Here with the help of Decision tree and to predict diseases the Naïve Bayes Algorithm is used. For procesing the data Random Forest, Decision Tree, and Naive Bayes. It provided an accuracy of 97.8% with the proposed system.

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